

FORMS OF CONNECTION PEDAGOGY WITH INTEGRATION SCIENCES

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Annotation: *The article discusses the concept and specificity of science, as well as some features of the functioning, integration and differentiation of science in modern conditions. The results of the division of sciences are the formation, to one degree or another of new industries. Separated independent scientific disciplines.*

Key words: *integrated education, scientific research, activity.*

The need for a special consideration of this problem is caused by the needs of practice, the need to strengthen the predictive function of pedagogical research, their impact on the practice of teaching and education. Of the whole complex of connections that, in principle, could be analyzed (connections of generation, transformation, structure, functioning, development, management), it is advisable to focus on the connections of functioning and development, since social needs are primarily that the education system and pedagogical science developed in the interests of the individual, society and the state.

Pedagogy, of course, cannot stand aside from the trend towards integration inherent in our time in all branches of science. However, it is this trend that makes the problem of identifying the specifics of pedagogy, its own scientific status and its own scientific content especially relevant, since what is not differentiated cannot be integrated. In order to combine efforts in a comprehensive solution of the problems now facing the school and pedagogy, it is necessary that each participant in this work determine their place in the overall work and the nature of the expected results of their activities. Thus, differentiation and integration are two sides of a single process.

Only an integrative science that holistically reflects a certain area of social practice can provide a direct and effective way out into this practice. Integrity means the internal unity of the object, its differentiation from the environment. Integration should not lead to "erosion" of pedagogical theory. The attraction and use of material and methods of other sciences should proceed from the needs of pedagogy itself, be

based on taking into account its own problems, tasks and opportunities, and not on general considerations like "why don't we try it."

В предыдущей главе говорилось: чтобы опережать и преобразовывать в соответствии с потребностями человека и общества наличный практический опыт, педагогическая наука должна использовать все богатство социального опыта в целом и отражение этого опыта в научном знании. Наряду с учетом отраженных в педагогической науке возможностей и закономерностей педагогической деятельности необходимы общефилософские знания, знание о методах научного познания, результаты специальных методологических исследований, социологические, психологические знания и т.д. In the previous chapter, it was said that in order to get ahead of and transform existing practical experience in accordance with the needs of man and society, pedagogical science must use the entire wealth of social experience as a whole and the reflection of this experience in scientific knowledge. Along with taking into account the possibilities and patterns of pedagogical activity reflected in pedagogical science, general philosophical knowledge, knowledge about the methods of scientific knowledge, the results of special methodological studies, sociological, psychological knowledge, etc. are necessary. A simple comparison of ready-made pedagogical knowledge with the same knowledge from related scientific fields cannot give an understanding of the true relationship of pedagogy with other sciences.

This correlation can be revealed only by analyzing the real specifics and the mechanism of using knowledge from various branches of science in the process of various types of pedagogical research on the theory of education, didactics, methods, school studies, etc. It is only in the context of research activities that it is possible to identify the forms of connection between pedagogy and other sciences. This requires a specific methodological analysis of the relationship of pedagogy with other sciences in their dynamics, in the system of research work aimed at substantiating pedagogical practice.

There are four main forms of such a connection in the literature¹. The most important of them is the use by pedagogy of the main ideas, theoretical provisions, generalizing the conclusions of other sciences.

First of all, pedagogy focuses on philosophy and sociological theory, which performs a methodological function in relation to pedagogy.

The second form of communication between pedagogy and other sciences is the use of research methods used in these sciences. In fact, any method of theoretical or empirical research can find application in scientific work in pedagogy, since in the conditions of integration of sciences, research methods very quickly become general

scientific. A combination of methods, the sequence of their application in accordance with the logic of pedagogical research, can be specific for pedagogy. Another form of connection between pedagogy and other branches of knowledge is the use of data from certain sciences, the specific results of their research: psychology, physiology of higher nervous activity, and sociology. More detailed ways of using such results will be shown in the further presentation using the example of the relationship between pedagogy and psychology.

A comprehensive study is understood as: a) a study that covers a number of problems (objects, phenomena) that are similar in nature or goals of study; b) a study in which the same object is considered from different points of view, from the positions of different scientific disciplines. Complex research work in the second meaning of this term is the study of a problem carried out by a team or a set of teams of scientists of various specialties working according to a single program and coordinating joint efforts to achieve common goals.

Pedagogical research should be considered as monodisciplinary in the sense that any "series of problems" in pedagogy is solved within the framework of this science. The use of data from other sciences in pedagogical research (as well as data from pedagogy in any other science) does not in itself make research interdisciplinary. Research does not become interdisciplinary even if, feeling, for example, the lack of available psychological knowledge to solve a certain problem, a teacher-researcher conducts psychological research within a pedagogical department or orders such research to a specialist psychologist. The position of the scientist changes, but not the subject and tasks of science and this study as a whole.

Monodisciplinary collective research is characterized by the following features:

1) orientation to the subject of this discipline, which is a unity of four components: a) the object of study as an area of reality, to which the researcher's activity is directed; b) empirical area, i.e. a set of various empirical descriptions of the properties and characteristics of an object accumulated by science to a given time; c) the task of the study; d) cognitive means;

2) the selection by each researcher of his own subject - certain aspects of the chosen object or connections in it, regarding which he must obtain new knowledge

3) the development of a methodological scheme of research, in which the sum of all individual studies would be necessary and sufficient to solve a common problem.

An interdisciplinary area, in relation to which an interdisciplinary research is carried out, can be such objects as space, the world ocean, personality, science. Various sciences distinguish their subjects in this object area. The object itself, in its specificity, in the multitude of its characteristics, is set as the goal of interdisciplinary research.

Thus, a distinction is made between the philosophical structure of personality and its psychological structure. Ways of purposeful creation of situations that contribute to the formation of a person's personality are studied by pedagogy, using sociological, psychological and other knowledge.

Interdisciplinary research may culminate in its transformation into a new scientific discipline. This happens if the problem identified in the course of the study of an interdisciplinary field reveals a permanent character and is realized methodologically. The new discipline will already be completely independent, retaining, in the figurative expression of E.M. Mirsky, “only in its history the memory of the interdisciplinary sins of youth”³. Apparently, this is exactly what happens in pedagogy. Her research is moving from interdisciplinary to monodisciplinary. It is known, for example, that the emergence of didactics, and along with it scientific pedagogy itself, coincided with the beginning of the general process of differentiation of the sciences, the separation of special sciences from the complex of philosophical knowledge. The next step in the development of didactics was characterized by a direct psychological substantiation of didactic provisions. Finally, at present, the status of didactics as one of the pedagogical scientific disciplines, the pedagogical theory of learning, has been sufficiently determined.

Collective pedagogical research can be complex and interdisciplinary to the extent that individual pedagogical disciplines have already emerged. Such a study can unite, for example, the efforts of specialists in didactics, methodology, and the theory of education. But in a broader sense, it will also be monodisciplinary, since, firstly, it is united by the subject of pedagogy, and secondly, in the end, the results of the study will be obtained in the subject of one of the pedagogical disciplines. An integrated approach to the educational process by a number of sciences without a single, integrative pedagogical position would be meaningless. Just as, for example, didactics does not cancel scientific methods, so a comprehensive study of the educational process does not exclude the possibility of a different approach to it from the side of the theory of education and from the side of didactics.

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